

THE USE OF NITROSO DERIVATIVES AS REAGENTS IN INORGANIC ANALYSIS. PART II.

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α - and β -Nitroso-naphthylamines are satisfactory reagents for the estimation of copper. Nickel also forms complexes with these reagents.

In Part I of this investigation, dealing with the quantitative estimation of cobalt, it has been mentioned that unlike the corresponding nitroso-naphthols α -nitroso- β -naphthylamine and β -nitroso- α -naphthylamine give copious precipitates with copper and nickel. We will deal with these metals one by one.

Precipitation of Copper.—With nitrosonephthylamines copper forms inner complex salts which are chocolate in colour, the β -complex being of a deeper shade. The precipitates are quantitative and directly weighable, insoluble in organic solvents and in dilute alkali, but they are soluble in acids, the β -complex being somewhat more soluble than the α -complex. With these reagents copper has been estimated gravimetrically in the directly weighable state and has also been quantitatively separated from cadmium, aluminium, chromium, zinc and manganese. The precipitates are of definite composition and reveal the following constitution.

Found α -complex : C, 59'11 ; H, 3'47 ; N, 13'99 ; Cu, 15'6 %

Found β -complex : C, 59'21 ; H, 3'40 ; N, 13'7 ; Cu, 15'57 %

(C₁₀H₇N₂O)₂ Cu requires: C, 59'23 ; H, 3'46 ; N, 13'82 ; Cu, 15'67 %

The copper solution containing 0'015-0'05g. of copper was diluted to 300 c.c. and 25 c.c. of 10% sodium-potassium tartrate were added. (Addition of tartrate was not essential when copper was estimated with α -nitroso compound. But tartrate should always be added when copper is estimated with the β -reagent and when it has to be separated from

other elements except cadmium). The solution was heated to boiling and the copper was thrown down with 1% alcoholic solution of the reagent. The solution was kept boiling for 20 minutes with constant stirring and then was allowed to settle. The precipitates were very granular and settled completely within a minute. The precipitation with the α -nitroso compound was always better and more satisfactory. The precipitate was then filtered through a sintered crucible, washed with a few c.c. of dilute alkali and then with boiling water and dried at 105° and weighed. It should be remembered that only the α -nitroso compound was used in cases of separations. Results are represented in Table I.

TABLE I.

Cu taken.	M/10 Soln. of and metal taken.	Cu ppt.		Calc.	Error.
		α -Reagent.	β -Reagent.		
0.03295 g.	...	0.2106 g.	...	0.2103 g.	+0.1%
0.03295	...	0.2098	...	"	-0.2
0.01647	...	0.1052	...	0.1051	Nil
0.01647	...	0.1052	...	0.1051	Nil
0.03295	...	...	0.2110 g.	0.2103	+0.3
0.01647	...	...	0.1054	0.1051	+0.2
0.01647	...	...	0.1050	0.1051	Nil
0.03295	5 c.c. CdSO ₄	0.2104	...	0.2103	Nil
0.03295	"	0.2056	...	0.1051	
0.01647	4 c.c. CdSO ₄	0.1052	...	0.1051	Nil
0.01647	5 c.c. ZnSO ₄	0.1054	...	0.1051	+0.3
0.03295	5 c.c. MnSO ₄	0.2104	...	0.2103	Nil
0.01647	5 c.c. Alum	0.1054	...	0.1051	+0.25
0.01647	5 c.c. Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	0.1055	...	0.1051	+0.3
0.01647	5 c.c. SbCl ₃	0.1054	...	0.1051	+0.2
0.01647	...	0.1050	...	0.1051	Nil

As the results of estimations are very accurate, the reagents may be freely recommended for gravimetric estimation of copper and for its separation from other elements, particularly cadmium. The α -nitroso compound is comparable to, if not better than, the best of copper reagents at present used for quantitative estimation of the metal.

Precipitation of Nickel.

The process of estimation was the same as in the case of copper. But the results of direct weighing were not always accurate. The complexes were, therefore, filtered through gravimetric filter papers, washed as usual, dried, ignited and the residue on the crucible moistened with a few drops of nitric acid and then ignited again to nickellic oxide NiO and weighed. In separating from other elements, buffering with tartrate, prior to the precipitation, was essential. The α -complex was black and the β -complex was light chocolate in colour. They are not soluble in organic solvents and are less soluble in acids than the corresponding copper complexes.

TABLE II.

Ni taken	<i>M/10</i> -Soln. of the 2nd metal taken.	Wt. of nickel oxide		Calc.	Error.
		α -Reagent.	β -Reagent.		
0.02896 g.	...	...	0.0369 g.	0.0369 g.	Nil
0.02896	...	...	0.0368	0.0369	-0.3%
0.04054	...	...	0.0518	0.0516	+0.4
0.04054	...	...	0.0519	0.0516	+0.5
0.02896	5 c.c. <i>M/10</i> -ZnSO ₄	0.0373 g.	...	0.0369	+1
0.02896	5 c.c. <i>M/10</i> -MnSO ₄	0.0363	...	0.0369	-1.5
0.02896	5 c.c. <i>M/10</i> -Alum	0.0369	...	0.0369	Nil
0.02896	5 c.c. <i>M/10</i> -Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	0.0374	...	0.0369	+1.3

The reagents are not entirely suitable or reliable for estimation.